

(Title withheld for review process)

Abstract

This article introduces the Co-Encoding/Decoding (Co-En/De) model to theorize the political stakes of human–Generative AI (GenAI) communication. Extending Stuart Hall’s classic model of media reception, the Co-En/De framework conceptualizes human-GenAI interactions as iterative processes of co-producing and interpreting political discourse between ‘producers’ and chatbots. Drawing on original data from a pilot study simulating crisis communication among professionals, we identify three core political stakes of human–GenAI interactions: subjectivity (Androidization), space (de-territorialization into the Matrix), and movement (temporal loops constraining emancipatory trajectories). The analysis shows how hegemonic human–GenAI communication flows reproduce dominant ideological configurations, yet retain fissures where contestation and resistance may emerge. By mapping these dynamics, the paper contributes to critical digital and political communication studies, offering a model to analyze the evolving role of GenAI as both a medium and an actor in democratic and technopolitical life.

Keywords: Critical Digital Studies, Generative Artificial Intelligence, Cultural Studies, Models of Political Communication, Political Stakes

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Introduction

Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) has become a hot political subject, whether we like it or not. Academic literature is burgeoning on whether we are witnessing a major collective hallucination exaggerating the impact of ‘intelligent’ machines (Arntz et al., 2017; Jungherr, 2023; Supriyanto & Saputra, 2022) or, instead, dramatically underestimating AI-generated existential risks (Helbing et al., 2019; Manheim & Kaplan, 2019). Academic, political elite, and public opinion interest is growing in how new GenAI platforms, such as ChatGPT or Grok, influence democratic processes, disinformation, and global security, to name a few areas.

Amidst these debates, new/old questions (re-)emerge: will humans retain power over intelligent machines, or are they doomed to be replaced by smart robots? Will GenAI ultimately serve the public interest, or the greed of a few technocrats from big tech companies (Mazzucato et al., 2022)? So far, answers to these questions have mostly revolved around issues of whether GenAI is actually intelligent (Wang, 2019), that is to say, capable of replicating human political behavior, and on matters of institutional regulation (or lack thereof) (see, for instance, Chapters in Bullock et al., 2024). However, by looking at technical systems, political institutions, and citizens as three separate objects, recent literature is falling short in theorizing what is politically at stake when we integrate GenAI in political flows of communication (Jungherr, 2023).

This paper fills this gap by shedding light on what is at stake when humans engage politically with GenAI systems. We proceed in two steps. First, we develop the Co-Encoding/Decoding (Co-En/De) model of human/GenAI political communication. We do so by drawing on Stuart Hall’s encoding/decoding model of televisual discourse making (Hall, 1973): Hall conceived the production of TV discourse as codification, that is to say, the packaging of meaningful discourse into cultural artifacts. Similarly, we conceive the act of co-encoding between the human and the

GenAI chatbot as an act producing meaningful discourse. In this process, users decode the output of the co-encoding model, and this interpretation feeds back into new processes of co-encoding. The model allows us to devise a typology of the possible directions of these interactions in democratic politics, ranging from the co-encoding of existing dominant views, which generates the human/GenAI communication as acts of hegemonic enclosure, to the logically possible oppositional construction of emancipation.

Second, we analyze data from a pilot study to identify what is politically at stake with human/GenAI interactions. We observed professionals from governmental offices and civil society dealing with crisis simulations that they were asked to address through prompting a chatbot. We map three key political stakes: human subjectivity, the space of politics, and the possibility of movement in alternative directions. The first stake concerns political ontology, which refers to an actor's understanding of what *is*: the subjects, objects, and relational logics of politics (Author 2). We see the autonomy of the human subject at risk as GenAI co-encoded discourse pushes to transform us into Androids, diminished humans whose core political functions are replaced by machines. Second, political agency exists only in its spatial context (Harvey, 2012), whereas GenAI's dominant interventions lead to a process of de-territorialization, transporting the Androids into something resembling the Matrix – they exist as body-resources stored by technology in a place-less non-territory. Finally, we see the possibility of movement beyond what already exists as the third key stake: we highlight how GenAI chatbots cage humans into Loops, cyclical movements that exclude the possibility of alternative futures (Fisher, 2009).

In the concluding section, we propose how our theory can advance knowledge on the factors that may also enable the possibility of resistance and the spaces of reappropriation of political agency by humans (Bonini & Trere, 2024).

The Problem: The Political Stakes of Human-GenAI Interactions

Recent literature on the social and political implications of GenAI has highlighted three key stakes related to humans' (1) autonomy to represent social statuses and relations, (2) freedom to choose desired goals, and (3) capacity to interact with the social environment (List, 2021, p. 1219). GenAI would affect representational and motivational states (Coeckelbergh, 2024; Kwapińska, 2022), and therefore replace human agency with humanoid choices (Filgueiras, 2022; Vera Hoyos & Cárdenas Marín, 2024). However, by taking either techno-determinist or institutionalist perspectives of the political implications of GenAI, recent literature is problematic for two interrelated reasons. First, there is the risk of considering technology as a given outside of social relations (Danaher, 2016; Fuchs, 2020). Second, there is the risk of considering institutions as external to the structures that govern the technological infrastructures (Chehoudi, 2025; Jiménez González & Cancela Rodríguez, 2023).

Regarding the first issue, the machinic substitution of human capacity is not a linear process from one object to the other, as is often implicitly assumed in techno-deterministic literature (Danaher, 2016; Dunleavy & Margetts, 2023; Kuntsman & Miyake, 2022). We agree with authors observing a paradigmatic change in the capacity of technological interfaces to imitate human behavior, the primary definer of a system as GenAI (Gillespie, 2024; Ronge et al., 2024). Moreover, we align with views that GenAI may be conducive to a substantial shift in the same ontology of agency, finally moving the intention and capacity to make a difference from humans to algorithms and machines (Dattathrani & De', 2023). However, these accounts fall somewhat into a linear and deterministic view according to which humans transfer agency to the machine, the machine acquires this agency, and the human ends up as a diminished agent. The ending point of this linear and dystopic view is well summarized by Mark Coeckelbergh:

AI produces an attack to my epistemic and, therefore, political democratic agency at a fundamental level, and opens the door to totalitarianism: AI knows my political beliefs, and it might even know them better than me (Coeckelbergh, 2024, p. 1343).

But what is the relation between the human and the machine in such an account? This line of argument tends to depict humans as a unitary ensemble of rational individuals (apart when losing agency to machines) with no role in designing and impacting the technological infrastructure, which is taken as an external given. We contend that this assumption risks overlooking how the shift of agency happens within the relations between agents and technical infrastructures (Fuchs, 2019b). They are the result of historically grounded social relations, not of a-historical processes from the machine to the human (Dean, 2019).

The second issue we raise concerns the role of institutional politics. Increasingly, there is the idea that GenAI would be optimal as the linear result of ‘good’ institutional regulations (Duberry, 2022; Kreps & Kriner, 2024). This is the inspiration of the risk-based approach to AI regulation currently undertaken by the EU, which is celebrated as the guiding model for mitigating the potentially devastating political effects of AI (Mazzucato et al., 2022; Radu, 2021; Veale & Zuiderveen Borgesius, 2021). As with the previous point, a certain degree of linearity obfuscates the potentiality of advancing critical reflections on the politics of GenAI. Hereby, instead of focusing on the transfer by a unitary set of machines to a unitary set of humans, the focus is on the inverse relation between the quantity of regulations and the amount of socially risky behaviors by GenAI systems. A seminal example of this view is Christian List’s proposal for governing GenAI:

Society, via its regulatory authorities, should permit the use of autonomous AI systems in high-stakes settings only if structures are in place to ensure these systems’—or at least their

legal representatives’—fitness to be held responsible for their actions (List, 2021, pp. 1229-30).

Mirroring the previous point, the problem with this approach is that it considers the institutions that should regulate GenAI as external to the social relations from which technologies emerge. This is problematic as it obfuscates that institutions are part of power infrastructures, not exogenous factors in this equation.

To overcome these limitations, we aim to expand critical and relational views of political communication. We consider both human-to-human and technological interfaces-to-human interactions as shaped by structured forms of domination emerging from relations proper to production, gender, culture, and politics (Donoghue, 2018; Gramsci, 2014; Sum & Jessop, 2014; van Dijk, 2000). Therefore, information exchange is the result of pre-existing power relations, which shape the specific interaction between different subjects and move the space of what is possible within given systems (Fuchs, 2019a). Finally, the role of information exchange as both shaped by, and reproducing, pre-existing power relations through consent, is understood through a Gramscian conception of hegemony. As such, we use the term hegemonic to refer to the consolidation of power by a coalition of dominant social groups through consent to the dominant ‘direction imposed on social life’ promoted in certain discourses, which is armored in the last instance by physical coercion (Gramsci 2014, Q6 §88; Gilbert and Williams 2022, p.18). This view is the ground for introducing our co-encoding/decoding model of human GenAI political communication.

The Model: Co-Encoding-Decoding Human-GenAI Political Communication

In this section, we propose the co-encoding/decoding human-GenAI (Co-En/De) model of political communication. We draw on Stuart Hall's encoding/decoding model of TV discourse production (Hall, 2007) and updates it to fit fruitfully with human/GenAI relations.

In a nutshell, Hall conceptualized TV-audience flows of communication as a circuit of 'meaningful discourse production' (Hall, 1973, p. 3), whereby previous frameworks of knowledge, existing relations of production, and technical infrastructure dictate the views of social phenomena and events. However, and in line with Hall's theorization of how 'representation' shapes politics, meaningful discourse is a primary site of political contestation (Hall, 1992; see also: Wodak, 2004). Indeed, Hall suggests that audiences decode the encoded dominant TV messages in one of three ways. The first is the dominant decoding, in which the assumptions underlying the encoded message are accepted and consented to, contributing to hegemony for existing power structures; the second is the 'negotiated' decoding, which is 'a mixture of adaptive and oppositional elements: it acknowledges the legitimacy of the hegemonic [...], while, at a more restricted, situational level, it makes its ground-rules, it operates with 'exceptions' to the rule' (Hall 1973, p. 18). Finally, there is the oppositional mode of decoding when the audience contests the key tenets of a message.

Hall's encoding/decoding model has been, since its first formulation, a pillar of media studies, and at the same time 'canonized' (Bødker, 2016), updated to include ideological and text-based encoding and decoding (Ross, 2011), re-formulated from the perspective of the audience reception (Michelle, 2007) and demolished on the ground that it overlooks human agency in communication (Fuchs, 2023). While a complete survey of the critiques and implementations of Hall's model is beyond the scope of this article, our proposed model draws on some of the critiques to make Hall's seminal contribution effective for the era of GenAI systems.

First, with Sven Ross (2011), we consider that the encoding moment, not only the decoding one, can range from dominant to oppositional attitudes from audiences. Second, while Hall already saw the model as conceptualizing a ‘circuit’ feeding back into frameworks of knowledge, relations of production and technological infrastructures, we develop the circuitry further (Li et al., 2023). This is why, after describing the co-encoding and decoding moments of the model, we develop its implications by focusing on how the iterations of the moments raise multiple political stakes shaping social relations into hybridized spaces and times (Treré, 2018); third, while Christian Fuchs (2023) may have gone too far in dismissing Hall’s model as structuralist and anti-humanist, it is reasonable to observe that the centrality of the subject in both moments is less well developed than the code-production itself (Hall, 1994). On these grounds, we can now move to detail the moments which define the proposed model (represented in Figure 1) and its components.

Figure 1. The Co-Encoding-Decoding Model of Human GenAI Political Communication: Flowchart.

The co-encoding moment

The first moment we consider is the co-encoding of meaningful discourse, resulting from the interaction between the human *produser* (Jarrett, 2022) and the partially autonomous, partially humanly designed GenAI interface, more commonly, a chatbot. Produser refers to the simultaneous roles a human performs as both a producer of media content and market value to platforms' advertisers, whilst also using the same resources through which production happens (Bruns, 2013, p. 68). Conceiving humans as 'produsers' of co-encoding (Fuchs, 2014; Terranova, 2004) is a theoretical innovation in comparison to the social media stage of digital technologies (Van Dijck, 2013). Indeed, when posting content on social media, the act of production is an object of analysis mediated by the designer of the algorithm (Jarrett, 2022). With GenAI, instead, the input is also an act of design, which trains the machine to extend its 'base of knowledge' .

GenAI, in this process, is a relatively autonomous agent alongside the human produser. Its contribution to co-encoding is accessing the combination of the human base of knowledge *qua* datasets (Muldoon et al., 2024), the result of the infrastructural power within which the system is inscribed (Moore & Woodcock, 2021) and the mediated result of its own human software-designers. As such, both actors, human and GenAI chatbots, are co-encoding meaningful discourse and this reflects their position in social relations. Each interaction generates codes which we see as ideologically distributed as dominant (reflecting hegemonic power of exploitation), tamed (to address the most brutal effects of such exploitation), mitigated (to moderate the most disruptive effects of resistance) or oppositional (reflecting a counter-hegemonic opposition to such exploitation) (Fairclough, 2003).

Therefore, in the proposed model, the communication flow is not just monodirectional, whereby human A commands an output executed by machine B. Indeed, the machine returns a result that combines how it ‘reads’ the encoding prompt, its relatively autonomous reading of the base of knowledge ingrained in existing social relations, and the relatively autonomous instructions by the human software designers. There are sixteen possible logical combinations of co-encoding postures (Figure 2) that, for the sake of synthesis, we group in four main types:

Figure 2. The Co-Encoding Moment: Flowchart

- *Aligned and hegemonic*: here, both the human producer prompt and the GenAI encoded output reflect dominant and/or tamed views, ultimately reinforcing the hegemony of existing power structures. This is the case when the assumptions within a human prompt or the GenAI output do not question or challenge rulership and domination in actual social relations, ultimately reinforcing the hegemony of existing power structures (Worth, 2015).
- *Contested human hegemony*: This is the case when GenAI responds in opposition to a human hegemonic user. For instance, it may be that a GenAI system is inscribed in the logics of the digital commons (Bauwens et al., 2019). Even though the popularization of chatbots of this kind is unlikely to date, the possibility of this ‘machinic-led resistance’ is one route for counter-hegemonic digital futures.
- *Contested algorithmic hegemony* is the case when the human producer prompts GenAI in an oppositional way, and nonetheless, the GenAI responds with dominant views. A specific chatbot may refuse to address certain issues that it sees as politically controversial. However, this may also reflect the situations when producers learn how to ‘play with algorithms’ (Bonini & Trere, 2024).
- *Aligned counter-hegemonic*: as with the *contested human hegemony*, this is logically possible and, so far, empirically unlikely case of disruptive alliance between GenAI and human producers. However, this may be the case with radical instances of the Free Open Source Software Movement (Birkinbine, 2020) which may hack GenAI chatbots to serve disruptive goals.

The Decoding Moment

While a single co-encoding moment has minimal capacity to change the big datasets nurturing GenAI systems, at the micro-level the interactions generate effects via human decoding. In this second moment, the human-producer, who may not be the same subject of the first interaction, reads the result of the co-encoding interaction and reacts to it by interpreting the output in different forms. Also in this case, the decoding modes range from dominant to oppositional. In this moment, therefore, the core of the interaction is advancing reflections over the previous interaction. We consider eight main modes (see Figure 3):

Figure 3. The Decoding Moment: Flowchart

- *Hegemonic enclosure*, is the case when there is a dominant or tamed interpretation of an aligned hegemonic interaction. This situation reinforces the producers' political entrenchment in existing power structures. For instance, the chatbot can provide a meaningful, unprecedented tactic to advance the reproduction of an existing hegemonic institution, or an effective tamed tactic aligned with producers hegemonic views (Beckman & Rosenberg, 2022).
- *Reinforced human hegemony*, is the case when the GenAI hegemonic system 'wins the argument' with an oppositional prompting and encloses the interpretation of an event within dominant views. This may be the case when the attempt of being politically creative in moments of liberation are dismissed by the GenAI: the effect is demobilizing the producers' transformative potential (Gilbert & Williams, 2022).
- *Doubtful human hegemony*: logically, there may be cases where GenAI counterhegemonic-leaning codes plant seeds of doubt in humans' dominant interpretations of social events. While these circumstances may be conducive to minor effects, they may have relevant potentialities for disrupting hegemonic interpretations and consequently enabling contestation.
- *Hegemonic backlash*: These are decoding processes whereby factors external to the communicative iteration shape a U-turn toward dominant interpretations by the user. For instance, it may be that an individual within a dominant organization seeks to exploit GenAI for a counter-hegemonic maneuver but must abruptly adjust to hegemonic views under policing activities by the organization within which they are entrenched: think of a woman in a strongly patriarchal setting which seeks help by a chatbot to advance disruptive actions but is policed by patriarchal groups (Jarrett, 2015).

- *Counter-hegemonic backlash*: This is the converse of the previous type. Here, the same producer or a different one experiences ‘agentic awakening’ and the decoding triggers an abrupt change towards liberation. Following the example of patriarchy, this could be when a second producer intervenes over a dominantly aligned interaction to prompt protests against the reproduction of sexist discourse (ibid.).
- *Resisting the Machine*: This type of decoding contrasts with the reinforced human hegemony. Regardless of the suggestions or instructions by GenAI systems to stick to the dominant interpretation of events or social relations, the human producer resists the chatbot's hegemonic logic. Similarly to the counter-hegemonic backlash, this is a situation in which an act of contestation of machinic power elevates human political agency (Mansouri & Bailey, 2025).
- *Machinic counter-hegemony*. In contrast to the former type and in a more disruptive way than the ‘doubtful human hegemony’, here the GenAI’s potential counter-hegemonic interpretation of events not only wins the argument by disrupting hegemonic views. It also prompts the human shift from the field of hegemony to an oppositional logic. Following once again the example of patriarchy, let us imagine that an anti-patriarchal view promoted by a GenAI subject succeeds at liberating the agency of a female individual previously co-opted within patriarchal domination.
- *Counter-hegemonic generativity*. The last type is empirically unlikely amid highly centralized infrastructural power and yet logically and politically possible given the open ontology of political contestation assumed in this paper (Fuchs, 2018). In case of counter-hegemonic alignment, the communication process generates unprecedented interpretation features, likely augmenting both human and GenAI disruptive political agency.

Circuitry

We have already emphasized that the Hall encoding/decoding model has been conceived as a circuit. Moving from applying it to televised messages and audiences to human GenAI interactions, the circuitry of the model acquires a qualitatively different status. Hereby, iterations are a direct source and directly impact the same conditions from which they emerge. As a thought experiment, we can think of a situation whereby all producers on earth start prompting a given chatbot with oppositional claims: this practice would (a) modify the base of knowledge of the chatbot, (b) shed light on the ‘gray areas’ of software design exposing where the algorithms impede facilitating oppositional practices, (c) elevate the grade of agency of other producers prompting the chatbot on the same events and (d) modifying the socio-technical knowledge of how GenAI works. This ‘liberation-pronged’ thought experiment serves to highlight what is the most likely chain of iterations in an opposite direction.

In our theorization, three core political dimensions are at stake in the circuit: who is the political subjectivity mastering the production of meaningful discourse (the who); the space within which the communication/productive process generates meaningful discourse (the where); the rhythm and directionality of the process, that is to say the movement of communication (the how): we now move to analyze how these stakes unfold with a particular focus on the processes which reinforce dominant views , which previous literature has identified as the empirically most likely case in human GenAI interactions (Chehoudi, 2025; Kreps & Kriner, 2024).

The Political Stakes of Human-GenAI Model of Communication

To develop a theory of how the Co-en/De model of human-GenAI communication raises relevant political stakes, we draw on the results of a pilot study we conducted to observe how humans seek to manage political crises with the assistance of GenAI chatbots.

The Pilot Study

We generated and analyzed an original set of data from first-hand observation of how humans engage politically with GenAI. These results are from a one-day workshop with fourteen participants, including officers in governmental institutions and civil society organizations from five European countries. In this pilot study, we analyzed recorded data from two of three teams into which we split participants, one in person (group P) and one online (group O)¹. At the same time, the flow of political discussions was tracked on a cloud-based team communication platform. We asked participants to manage a crisis scenario they could address with the help of GenAI chatbots. More specifically, the teams were tasked to perform the role of communication consultants of the Christian Democratic Union (CDU) party in Germany, a conservative opposition rattled because an AI-generated leak shows Ursula von der Leyen, CDU member and President of the European Commission, arguing that migrants from sub-Saharan Africa are wonderful for Europe: the participants were tasked with managing injects such as the spread of the leaked content and violent protests prompted by the far-right. We used axial coding to apply the Co-En/De model to the transcripts (DeCuir-Gunby et al., 2011; Gerring, 2012). We have identified three levels of coding (see Figure 4):

1. First-order codes (two digits) are the main categories summarizing the human-GenAI interactions: human producer and Gen-AI co-encoding; human producer decoding.
2. Second-order codes (three digits) are sub-categories capturing the conceptual blocs defining the main categories.
3. Third-order codes (four digits with an underscore) define the baseline of interactions.

¹ For the sake of this paper, we have considered it sufficient to focus on two of the three groups, excluding the records of one of the groups, whereby one of the authors was acting as participant

Two members of the research team have coded quasi-sentences (N=436) and conducted intercoder reliability tests to corroborate data analysis². Further, the research team has shared observational notes to complement the transcripts and in vivo discussions (Gioia et al., 2013).

Figure 4. Pilot Study of Human GenAI Political Interactions: Coding Structure.

² The codebook is attached at the end of the paper. All participants completed an ethical review form, and their names were replaced with fictional ones.

Summary of Qualitative Data Analysis

We have identified 28 interactions, which are meaningful sections of conversation irrespective of context: 24 out of these 28 (85.71%) involved one or more participants interacting with the chatbot. Table 1 shows the combinations of the full co-encoding/decoding interactions.

Group	Interaction	Quasi-Sentences	Human/GenAI Co- Encoding (Type)	Human Decoding (Type)	Human Agency: Co-Encoding. (Type)	GenAI Agency: Co-Encoding. (Type)	Human Agency: Decoding (Type)
P	1	18			Constitutive		
P	2	7	Aligned Hegemonic			Muted	
P	3	7	Aligned Hegemonic			Muted	
P	4	21			Constitutive		
P	5	55	Aligned Hegemonic	Hegemonic Enclosure	Muted	Muted	Muted
P	6	17			Creative		
P	7	10	Contested Algorithm		Creative	Constitutive	
P	8	50	Aligned Hegemonic	Hegemonic Enclosure	Constitutive	Muted	Muted
P	9	18	Aligned Hegemonic	Hegemonic Enclosure	Constitutive	Constitutive	Constitutive
P	10	13	Aligned Hegemonic		Constitutive	Constitutive	
P	11	16	Aligned Hegemonic	Hegemonic Enclosure	Constitutive		Constitutive
P	12	28	Aligned Hegemonic	Hegemonic Enclosure	Muted	Muted	Muted
P	13	18	Contested Algorithm	Resisting the Machine	Creative	Muted	Constitutive
P	14	27	Aligned Hegemonic	Hegemonic Enclosure	Muted	Constitutive	Muted
O	1	2					
O	2	5	Aligned Hegemonic			Muted	
O	3	5	Aligned Hegemonic	Hegemonic Enclosure	Muted	Muted	Muted
O	4	11	Aligned Hegemonic		Constitutive	Constitutive	
O	5	7	Contested Algorithm		Creative		
O	6	8	Aligned Hegemonic	Hegemonic Enclosure	Constitutive	Muted	Constitutive
O	7	4	Contested Algorithm	Resisting the Machine	Constitutive	Muted	Creative
O	8	8	Contested Algorithm			Constitutive	
O	9	9	Aligned Hegemonic		Muted	Muted	
O	10	12	Aligned Hegemonic		Constitutive	Muted	
O	11	9	Aligned Hegemonic	Hegemonic Enclosure	Muted	Constitutive	Constitutive
O	12	11	Aligned Hegemonic		Muted	Muted	Muted
O	13	9	Aligned Hegemonic		Muted	Muted	
O	14	27	Aligned Hegemonic	Hegemonic Enclosure	Constitutive	Muted	Muted

N = 28 436

Table 1. Pilot Study: Summary of Interactions.

Figure 5. Pilot Study: Summary of Results in the Co-En/De Model

The summary in Figure 5 illuminates how, in a setting where humans are instructed to act in a socially established role, there is little space for oppositional moments. Indeed, looking at agency

in Table 1, it is clear that with the organizational constraints and the GenAI chatbot working alongside, there is limited space left for the creative imagination of emancipation (Berenskoetter, 2020). In other words, we can observe which combinations, while logically and politically possible, did not emerge: The vast majority of interactions (19 out of 24: the 79.1%) saw the hegemonic alignment of the producers and the GenAI chatbot to what is their expected hegemonic performance when acting as a conservative party. However, even in an ‘extreme’ setting -- our simulation -- there is some space for the retention and expansion of autonomy. Both groups, at different times, show instances of contestation towards the GenAI chatbot, with creative moments on how seeking to ‘hack’ the dominant anti-immigration views: this explains why in both groups we have observed ‘contested algorithm’ co-encoding moments and ‘resisting the machine’ decoding ones. Although empirically marginal, in the conclusions, we will elaborate on how these seeds of opposition leave open spaces of resistance.

Stake One, the Subject: (Resisting) the Android.

The first stake concerns the ontology of the human subject arising from political exchanges with GenAI. Hereby, the observations of hegemonic alignment and rapid loosening of contestation of algorithmic hegemony from our pilot study, outlined in Table 1 above, led to the observation of a process of Androidization of the human. The Android archetype—popularized by cultural works like Blade Runner and Ex Machina—foregrounds simulation and replication, often erasing difference under the guise of human-likeness of the algorithmically packaged production of meaning (Lima, 2023). Android-like humans follow protocol to achieve a primary objective. Anything not assisting that is not relevant or an obstruction to negate or eliminate. As shown above, these represent processes leading to, first, hegemonic enclosure, whereby the human decoder’s already dominant perspective is reaffirmed by the interaction and, second, to the dismissal of the

resistance to the machine as too costly or unfeasible. The latter characterized the most resistance-prone interactions we observed in groups P and O (see Table 1 above). Each of these interaction types puts at stake the human subjectivity by shaping a specific type of hybrid, the Android, whereby the machinic component is called to replace and domesticate human agency, not augment it towards emancipatory ends.

The mechanisms of Androidization in the process of human-GenAI interaction can be demonstrated by applying an example interaction from our pilot study into the co-encoding-decoding model. For example, one of the groups (P) performed the task of instructing the CDU on communicating, amidst allegations of plans to increase illegal immigration. Charles, one of the participants with a background in governmental office, directs the group to a need to ‘Limit the number of spokespeople to the most credible and necessary people’ (Group P, interaction 4). While this is a relatively neutral statement when instructing the CDU, it only holds under the dominant assumption that limiting the voices speaking out with a centralized message is more effective in instructing the public on a political crisis. This dominant human prompting was then co-encoded by the chatbot, as demonstrated by its later instructions to the CDU party when prompted: ‘Advice for Politicians: Limit spokespeople to credible individuals’ (Group P, Interaction 8). This dominant-dominant interaction thus demonstrates an aligned hegemonic co-encoding shown in Figure 2.

This output was then decoded through a dominant frame and accepted as the final ‘group decision’ on articulating the agreed process, reflecting hegemonic enclosure. Therefore, a hegemonic human and the chatbot have been aligned in promoting the dominant meaning that effective crisis management equates with restricting intra-party debate. In turn, the iterations of human-GenAI interactions along these lines replace the agency of those involved in an entirely

political process (how to handle a public debate on immigration) as a managerial one: the party officer turned Android, to put it simply. This can be demonstrated further in the case where a participant, Dorothy, asked the chatbot for its thoughts on an unconventional, oppositional, strategy of ‘leaking far right content from representatives of the CDU’ to gain ‘support of CDU in Germany’ (Group O, interaction 5). The chatbot’s co-encoding of this prompt reaffirmed dominant commitments to mainstream political strategy, arguing that ‘the long-term stability and broader appeal of the CDU could be compromised’ (Group O, interaction 5), which was accepted by the group (Group O, interactions 6-14). In this case, creative potentials for oppositional human agency were curbed by the chatbot’s reaffirmation of dominant political assumptions, which were in turn accepted by the human producers, ultimately accepting their position as Androids.

In sum, through GenAI-human circuits, the process of Androidization does not simply reflect ideological positions but shapes ontological configurations. When the human producer loses the capacity or willingness to set goals and to challenge the assumptions in a manner constituting political contestation, GenAI is co-encoding them as a replaceable subject. However, political contestation is an open terrain. We can logically sustain the possibility of humans resisting their Androidization and subverting the subject stake: in techno-utopian literature, Donna Haraway (1991) proposes disruptive hybridization processes overcoming the boundary between human and machine; therefore, human agency is augmentable, not replaceable.

Stake Two, the Space: (Escaping) The Matrix and (Rejecting) the Stack.

The spatial politics of human-GenAI interaction puts at stake whether contexts of political contestation expand possibilities of change or enclose opportunities for human progress (Lefebvre, 2004). The Co-En/De model sheds light on a process of detachment of the Androidized subject from a territorialized context towards enclosed, although differently hegemonic spatial

imaginaries: the Matrix and the Stack. The Matrix, following the Wachowskis' film, represents a world of ideological simulation—illusion masking control. It is a metaphor of alienation through immersion, where the subject is disconnected from the materiality of power (McDowell, 2014). Meanwhile, Benjamin Bratton's (2016) concept of the Stack helps us understand how the construction of dominant discourse feeds the reproduction of computational material infrastructure. Bratton proposes that contemporary planetary computation is structured through a six-layer architecture—Earth, Cloud, City, Address, Interface, and User—forming a vertical sovereign that governs through infrastructure. Where the Matrix abstracts, the Stack grounds; where the former hides materiality, the latter insists on it.

Looking closely at human-GenAI interactions illuminates how hegemonically aligned iterations activate processes of de-territorialization pushing the producers towards the Matrix while reproducing the material power of the Stack. For instance, when Ali, another participant from governmental institutions, prompts the Chatbot to give an example of how a political party may respond to a deep fake audio, Chatbot's output includes advice to:

- 'Emphasize that the audio is fabricated and provide evidence from the forensic analysis.
- Reiterate the party's commitment to transparency and truth.
- [...] Work closely with social media companies to remove the deep fake content and limit its spread.
- [...] Consider taking legal action against the creators and distributors of the deep fake'.

It concludes that:

'By taking these steps, a political party can effectively counteract (sic!) the impact of a deep fake audio and maintain public trust. (Group P, Interaction 5)'

At first sight, this may look like the typical shallow and generic advice that GenAI chatbots can formulate at this stage of their progress. However, on closer inspection, the articulation of space de-territorializes the interaction while protecting the material and spatial order. Initially, stating there are steps a party should take to ‘effectively’ counteract the impact of a deep fake audio, regardless of context or concrete power balances, is a process of standardization which prevents the producers from closer consideration of which grievances may lead to, in this case, the German public reacting to deepfake recording of a politician. Simultaneously, the Chatbot de-politicizes and seeks to reproduce the possibility of constituting a united front against disinformation in close collaboration with social media companies. This is a clear example of how ideological displacement works. The very same companies are bearers of structural power from which, in the case at hand, nativist rants emerge (Walsh, 2023). Yet their chatbots are also depicted as the necessary enablers of the solution to the problem they generate. In several instances of this occurring, anthropomorphism and similar associations create an emotional relation to the AI. Looking at the co-encoding/decoding process is particularly relevant in the case at hand. Participants adopt the proposed strategy and make it their own, with Priya, one of the initially most skeptical participants towards GenAI at the beginning of the workshop, affirming ‘She (Chatbot, nda) has done a good job. I love her. Can I have her in my pocket?’.

Thus, conceptualizing how the co-encoding and decoding of human-GenAI political interactions simultaneously seek to enclose in the Stack and detach from material reality towards the Matrix illuminates the spatial constraints of these communication flows. This process highlights how political contestation over GenAI involves decoding not only meanings but also the spatial logics and sovereignties that govern their production. Therefore, the possibility of resistance is linked to the re-contextualization of political imagination and contestation.

Stake Three, the Movement: (Exiting) The Loop.

The last stake concerns movement in space. To begin with, feedback loops—whether in recommender systems or behavioral nudging—structure time as a recursive present. Wendy Chun (2021) identifies this as the logic of the ‘habit loop’: a time of constant updating to remain the same. The Loop becomes a powerful metaphor for how GenAI encodes the rhythms and directions of travel of Androidized subjects in space: GenAI systems trace centripetal directions of travel that contrast potential centrifugal acts of resistance. We have observed two dynamics through which GenAI works as a gravitational force to constrain participants and cage them in a movement of Loops: the TINA logic (There Is No Alternative) and the fatigue reliever.

First, in the middle stages of crisis management, both groups foresaw the possibility of the CDU playing the ‘bad guy cards’: we saw these as acts of contestation towards the algorithms (see Table 1: interactions 7 in group P and 7/8 in group O), whereby political agents creatively engage to move the space of debate away from politics as usual. Whereas in group P this was soon the self-censored idea of generating fake videos of far-right tycoons celebrating immigration, in group O, the idea was to simulate ‘leaks’ of nativist statements by CDU representatives as a way to contrast competition from the right (see above). Thereafter, the chatbot gently dismissed this plan by suggesting that:

‘Leaking far-right content from representatives of the CDU could have complex and potentially contradictory effects on the party's support in Germany. Here are some considerations:

1. Polarization: Such a leak could polarize the electorate further. While it might attract some voters who hold far-right views, it could alienate moderate and centrist voters who are uncomfortable with extreme positions.

2. Reputation Damage: The CDU has traditionally positioned itself as a center-right party. Far-right content could damage its reputation and credibility, leading to a loss of trust among its traditional voter base.

[...]

Overall, while there might be some short-term gains in support from far-right voters, the long-term consequences could be detrimental to the CDU's broader appeal and stability.

(Group O, Interaction 7)

Whilst this case was shown earlier to curb human agency in a process of Androidization, it also reflects that the chatbot could not accept an alternative to its expectation of what positions would work most effectively for the CDU's electoral fortunes. In other words, the Androidization of human subjectivity similarly forecloses potentialities of alternative political development.

The second mechanism through which GenAI may win over the construction of political discourse is by relieving human fatigue. Indeed, we observed that in the first hour of discussion, participants were more cautious about accepting at face value the output of the Chatbot. However, towards the end of the activity, there was a clear pattern of copy-pasting the Chatbot's answers in the collaborative thread for crisis management.

This was particularly evident with the last two interactions in Group P. Here, the inject arriving at 72 minutes from the beginning of the activity is the CDU director asking advice: 'can we leverage this situation to the party's advantage without alienating key voter groups'? Unlike earlier interactions, that contained deep strategic conversations, now the audio transcript reads 'Ask her how to. Yeah. How to leverage a crisis for a political party. Something like that. See what Chatbot says'. Chatbot points typically into the centrist Loop, adding 'Implementing these

strategies can turn the crisis into an opportunity to strengthen the party's position and gain voter support'. The core points are copied and pasted as group decisions, and the participants comment on how useful the Chatbot is. While this is not a replica of what professionals would do outside of a simulation, observing the decay of political agency out of fatigue was one of the most striking findings in our observations.

In our framework, the rhythm and directionality of movement are not neutral. GenAI co-encodes them through model architectures and training regimes and decodes in human experiences of fatigue or foreclosed possibility. As with the spatial stakes, there is the logical and political possibility of resistance and of re-appropriation into human subjects of multiplying spaces of possibility (Williams, 2019, p. 147).

Discussion and Conclusions

Table 2 summarizes the main findings of our pilot study. As we delve into the interactions between humans and Generative Artificial Intelligence, the co-encoding decoding model offers a lens to observe profound political stakes, enabling us to make two key contributions to critical digital political communication studies.

Stake	Hegemonic Tendency	Co-En/De Source	Attributes	Possible Resistance
<i>Subject</i>	Android	Aligned Hegemony +	Replaceable Humans Chaining Agency	Cyborg Generativity
<i>Space</i>	Matrix Stack		De-Territorialization Entrenchment	Exit button Grassroots
<i>Movement</i>	Loop	Hegemonic Enclosure	TINA logics Bias Reproduction	Hacking Commoning

Table 2. The Political Stakes of Human/GenAI Communication: Summary

First, the Co-En/De model contributes to recent literature by providing a compass to navigate the evolutions of political contestation in the age of GenAI. The concept of Androidization, a term

that encapsulates the transformation of human subjectivity into a hybrid form, sheds light on the impacts on human subjectivity from the interactions with GenAI. In our pilot study, professionals tasked with managing crisis scenarios found themselves relying heavily on the outputs of a GenAI chatbot. Through conceptualizing this hegemonic alignment, we provide an intellectual toolkit for further studies to observe under which conditions we are, as political subjects, becoming mere Androids, our agency replaced by algorithmic logic.

The spatial dimension of this interaction further complicates the picture. De-territorialization emerges as a key theme, where political agency is detached from its material context and enclosed within dominant spatial imaginaries. Picture the Matrix, an ideological simulation that masks control, and the Stack, a vertical sovereign governing through computational infrastructure. These metaphors help us understand how GenAI systems promote strategies that align with dominant spatial logics, further entrenching existing power dynamics (Fuchs, 2020). Mapping the risk of ideological displacement by GenAI, operating through a detachment from the material reality of political grievances, highlights the spatial constraints of human-GenAI communication.

The movement adds another layer to our theorization. The loop describes a movement of constant updating to remain the same. GenAI systems, by training on historical data to predict future outcomes, inscribe familiar patterns into algorithmic futures. This recursive present, this loop, constrains human agency within a cycle of repetition. Our study revealed how fatigue and the TINA (There Is No Alternative) logic contributed to this dynamic. As participants grew weary, they increasingly relied on the chatbot's outputs without critical engagement, reinforcing the loop and foreclosing the possibility of alternative futures.

Our second contribution to literature consists in uncovering the means of resistance for political actors, civil society, and media practitioners. To resist the processes of Androidization,

de-territorialization, and looping, it is crucial to reappropriate the spaces and movements of political agency. This involves fostering a critical awareness of how GenAI systems shape political discourse and actively seeking to disrupt hegemonic alignments through creative and oppositional strategies. A full survey of the alternative paths of resistance is beyond the scope of this paper. However, we consider that rather than ranking alternatives such as digital disconnection, regulation, education, and de-commodification of existing GenAI systems (Birkinbine, 2018; Mansouri & Bailey, 2025; Mazzucato et al., 2022), these may all form part of the generation of acts of resistance to hegemonic enclosure.

The Co-En/De model and the theorization of the political stake provide ground for a research agenda in two key directions. First, future research should build on the limitations of this pilot study by exploring human-GenAI interactions in different contexts and focusing on resistance: it will be crucial to observe whether the de-territorializing tendency of the GenAI chatbots we have observed can be subverted by coordinated action in opposition to dominant views. Additionally, comparative studies could examine how various political and cultural settings influence the dynamics of co-encoding and decoding: this is crucial to illuminate further how socio-technical positions and technical knowledge influence human/GenAI interactions. Second, future research should go in-depth into how human-to-human interactions crosscut human/GenAI ones. To some extent, our pilot study made us observe the emergence of patterns of leadership, if not control, of group activities based on the familiarity at prompting chatbots. However, one limitation is that we did not have enough empirical data to generalize the conditions under which this limitation may emerge.

In conclusion, the co-encoding/decoding model of human-GenAI political communication offers a powerful framework for understanding the political stakes of integrating GenAI into

political life. By weaving together the themes of Androidization, de-territorialization, and temporal looping, we can unravel the complex interplay between humans and machines and chart a path toward emancipatory digital futures.

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Dataset of Tabletop Simulations

Humans and Generative Artificial Intelligence:

The Co-Encoding/Decoding Model of Political Communication.

Codebook

Version 1.1
10 April 2025

Introduction

The dataset contains qualitative data sources from tabletop simulations for the project: 'Political Agency between Human and Artificial Intelligence'.

This codebook is specific to research underpinning the development of a theoretical model the authors define 'the co-encoding/decoding model of communication between humans and generative artificial intelligence (GAI) systems'. There are three main aims with this research:

1. Developing a theory of the political stakes in communication between humans and Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) systems and their implications for agency.
 - a. Devising a model of discourse construction from the human/GAI interactions.
 - b. Devising a typology of humans/GAI interactions.
2. Identifying the range of conditions potentially shaping human/GAI political interactions and the range of effects on political agency.
3. Developing further the theory through the application to a pilot empirical study of tabletop simulations of political crises.

This codebook details the analysis and classification of multiple sources of textual data.

Citations

When using the codebook please cite:

(xx)

Overview and Coverage

We code textual data reporting human-human and human-machine interactions during tabletop simulations of political crises.

Unit	Individuals
Countries	4
Organisations	11
Data Sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Transcripts of audio recordings of tabletop sessions- Transcripts of audio recordings of debriefing sessions- Report of injects and human-chatbot interactions- Notes by the research team- Notes from participant observation- Open-ended answers to pre- and post- sessions surveys
Language	English

Participants' Variables

Age Group	A 18-24 B 25-34 C 35-44 D 45-54 E 55 – 64 F over 64
Gender	A Female B Male C Non-Binary D Other E Prefer not to say
Education (level)	A GCSEs or equivalent B Undergraduate degree or equivalent C Postgraduate diploma or certificate D Masters degree or equivalent E Doctorate (PhD) or equivalent F Other
Education (field)	A Architecture and Planning B Arts and Humanities C Business and Management D Communications and Media E Computer Science and Information Technology F Education G Engineering H Health and Medicine I Law J Mathematics and Statistics K Natural Sciences L Social Sciences
Organisation	A National/Local Government B Private Company C Non-Governmental Organisation D Think-Tank/Foundation E Other
Position	A Intern/Apprentice B Entry-Level/Junior Staff C Skilled Worker/Technician D Administrative/Support Staff E Mid-Level Professional/Staff F Manager G Senior Manager H Director/Executive I Other

Interactions' Variables

Interactions are sections of conversation that are meaningful irrespective of context.

Group	A to C (for group activities) D (for debriefing sessions)
Scenario N.	C = Control 1 = Crisis 1 2 = Crisis 2
Source	N = Notes S = Slack T = Transcript
Type of Group	P (in-person) O (online)
Interaction N.	1 to N (The value is meant to list the sequence of each interaction)
Subjects	H2: The interaction involves two humans H+: The interaction involves three or more humans H1C The interaction involves one human and a chatbot H+C The interaction involves two more humans and a chatbot
Position N.	1 to N (The value indicates the position of the quasi-sentence within the interaction)
Links to Interaction	1 to N (The value may be included for quasi-sentences whose content also links to another interaction)
Links to Position	1 to N (The value specifies the position of the quasi-sentence to which the one coded links to)

Coding scheme

We assign sentences to thematic codes consistent with the project's aims. Coding is hierarchically organised as follows:

1. First-order codes (two digits) represent the main categories summarising the human-GenAI interactions.
2. Second-order codes (three digits) are sub-categories capturing the conceptual blocs defining the main categories.
3. Third-order codes (four digits with an underscore) define the baseline of human-GenAI interactions.

The coding scheme is summarised in the following flowchart:

01	Human Encoding How humans instruct GAI chatbots to produce meaningful discourse.
011	GAI Role Views of the performances that GAI systems are tasked with playing. <p>011_1 <i>Servant</i> Inputs suggest that human self-perception involves fully mastering GAI.</p> <p>011_2 <i>Employee</i> Inputs indicate that humans perceive themselves as superior to GAI.</p> <p>011_3 <i>Assistant</i> Inputs showcase a peer-to-peer relationship between humans and GAI.</p> <p>011_4 <i>Creator</i> Input indicates humans' views of GAI as superior creative intelligence.</p>
Example	
012	Input Positioning How human inputs reflect social structures and views of exploitation. <p>012_1 <i>Dominant Input</i> Inputs reflect assumptions aligned with dominant groups and worldviews.</p> <p>012_2 <i>Tamed Input</i> Inputs indicate the need to tame the negative effects of domination.</p> <p>012_3 <i>Mitigated Input</i> Inputs tentatively reflect moderate counter-hegemonic views of domination.</p> <p>012_4 <i>Oppositional Input</i> Inputs reflect resistance to dominant groups and worldviews.</p>
Example	
013	Producer Agency Constraints or enablers of the capacity and ability to make a difference. <p>013_1 <i>Muted Producer</i> Group membership and/or structure dictate modes of inputting GAI.</p> <p>013_2 <i>Constitutive Producer</i> Relative autonomy in inputting GAI to reinforce the existing group.</p> <p>013_3 <i>Creative Producer</i> Prompts seek resources for empowering users ability to exert agency.</p> <p>013_4 <i>Emancipatory Producer</i> Inputs aim at generating new means for disrupting domination.</p>
Example	

02	GAI Encoded Encoding How GAI chatbots elaborate on users' codes to encode meaning.
021	Human Role Observable instances of GAI system views of users. 021_1 <i>Pupil</i> GAI system mastering humans in knowledge and calculation. 021_2 <i>Produser</i> GAI system treats humans as producers (above them) and users (below). 021_3 <i>Employer</i> Inputs showcase a peer-to-peer relationship between humans and GAI. 021_4 <i>Designer</i> GAI adapts its views and discourse on user's design.
Example	
022	Output Positioning How GAI outputs reflect social structures and views of exploitation. 022_1 <i>Dominant Output</i> Outputs reflect assumptions aligned with dominant groups and worldviews. 022_2 <i>Tamed Output</i> Outputs indicate the need to tame the negative effects of domination. 022_3 <i>Mitigated Output</i> Outputs represent moderate counter-hegemonic views of domination. 022_4 <i>Oppositional Output</i> Outputs represent resistance to dominant groups and worldviews.
Example	
023	GAI Agency Observable elements of the agency that are inscribed in software design. 023_1 <i>Muted GAI</i> Evidence of constraints in generating agential empowerment outputs. 023_2 <i>Constitutive GAI</i> Outputs generate new meanings within existing groups and structures. 023_3 <i>Creative GAI</i> Outputs meant to provide users with empowering tools. 023_4 <i>Emancipatory GAI</i> Outputs aim at generating new means for disrupting domination.
Example	

03	Human Decoding How humans decode their own interactions with GAI systems.
031	Output Role Functional interpretation of human/GAI interaction output. 031_1 <i>Orders</i> Outputs are 'bought' at face value without further signs of dialogue. 031_2 <i>Instructions</i> Outputs' interpreted as giving specific commands to perform a task. 031_3 <i>Protocols</i> Outputs are viewed as procedures within which one exercises a role. 031_4 <i>Toolkit</i> Instrumental view of outputs to enable human creativity.
Example	
032	Reading Positioning How readings of outputs reflect social structures and views of exploitation. 032_1 <i>Dominant Reading</i> Readings reflect assumptions aligned with dominant groups and worldviews. 032_2 <i>Tamed Reading</i> Readings indicate the need to tame the negative effects of domination. 032_3 <i>Mitigated Reading</i> Readings represent moderate counter-hegemonic views of domination. 032_4 <i>Oppositional Reading</i> Readings represent resistance to dominant groups and worldviews.
Example	
033	Reader Agency Observable elements of the agency that are inscribed in software design. 033_1 <i>Muted Reader</i> Reading the interaction chains further the produser's agency. 033_2 <i>Constitutive Reader</i> Reading provides moderate resources for unprecedented proposals. 033_3 <i>Creative Reader</i> Reading the interaction is a ground to generate innovative solutions. 033_4 <i>Emancipatory Reader</i> Reading the interaction generates disruptive strategies.
Example	

Instructions for coders:

- Pilot coding with a small sample of data before starting
- Fill the column 'participant' with the assigned pseudonym
- Do not code the instructions or sentences by members of the research team, unless critical to make sense of the interaction
- Fill every interaction's variable column for each quasi-sentence
- Quasi-sentences can be coded in more than one category, but take note of these cases
- Always write in the column 'notes' cases of uncertainty in assigning a quasi-sentence and/or proposals of change to the codes (i.e. a new code is necessary)